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FOREIGN LANGUAGE LEARNING IN NON-LINGUISTIC UNIVERSITIES AS THE KEY TO PROFESSIONAL CULTURE FORMATION

Natalia Yu. LOGINOVA,

Russian State University of Tourism and Service (Moscow, Russia);

Senior Lecturer; e-mail: snare64@mail.ru

Tatiana V. KRYLOVA,

Moscow State University of Civil Engineering (National Research University); (Moscow, Russia);

Lecturer; e-mail: littlehowlet@gmail.com

Abstract. The issue of developing future specialists has been a longstanding subject of inquiry, driven by the evolving criteria used to delineate the concept of a future specialist. Typically, the exploration of challenges and tasks associated with cultivating future specialists entails a focus on enhancing cognitive abilities, personal attributes, motivation, and practical professional competencies. However, a pressing concern in Russia currently centers around the cultivation of ethical and spiritual values, along with shared cultural foundations among future specialists. This research paper aims to analyze the formation of cultural values within the context of shaping the professional culture of future specialists, and to examine how the development of communicative competence influences this process. Within this study, definitions of culture and professional culture are provided, elucidating the role of cultural development in shaping professional competence. The inquiry also delves into the relationship between the study of a foreign language at a non-linguistic university and the broader cultural development of future specialists. Emphasis is placed on the significance of fostering an understanding of fundamental humanitarian and communicative principles in the educational programs of Russian universities. Ultimately, it is concluded that, in non-linguistic university settings, the study of foreign languages as a distinct discipline significantly impacts the cultural and professional advancement of individuals in contemporary circumstances.

Keywords: culture, communication, professional culture, ethics, professional communication, professional competencies, foreign languages

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ИЗУЧЕНИЕ ИНОСТРАННОГО ЯЗЫКА В НЕЯЗЫКОВЫХ ВУЗАХ КАК КЛЮЧЕВОЙ ФАКТОР ФОРМИРОВАНИЯ ПРОФЕССИОНАЛЬНОЙ КУЛЬТУРЫ

ЛОГИНОВА Наталия Юрьевна,

Российский государственный университет туризма и сервиса (Москва, РФ);

Старший преподаватель; e-mail: snare64@mail.ru

КРЫЛОВА Татьяна Вадимовна,

Национальный исследовательский Московский государственный строительный университет (Москва, РФ);

Преподаватель; e-mail: littlehowlet@gmail.com

Аннотация. Проблема формирования будущих специалистов является предметом изучения на протяжении длительного времени. Это обусловлено постоянно изменяющимися требованиями к определению концепции будущего специалиста. Как правило, при рассмотрении проблем и задач, связанных с формированием будущих специалистов, внимание акцентируется на развитии когнитивных способностей, личных качеств, мотивации и практических профессиональных навыков. Тем не менее, в настоящее время в России остро стоит вопрос о проблеме формирования этических и духовных ценностей и общих культурных основ у будущих специалистов. В данной статье объектом исследования является анализ процесса формирования культурных ценностей в рамках формирования профессиональной культуры будущего специалиста и влияние развития коммуникативной компетенции на данный процесс. В рамках данного исследования дается определение культуры, профессиональной культуры и определяется место культурного развития личности в процессе формирования профессиональной компетенции. Ставится вопрос о взаимосвязи между изучением иностранного языка в неязыковом вузе и общим культурным развитием будущего специалиста, подчеркивается важность развития понимания основных гуманитарных и коммуникативных основ в рамках образовательных программ российских вузов. Определяется, что в неязыковых вузах изучение иностранных языков как отдельной дисциплины оказывает наиболее глубокое влияние на культурное и профессиональное развитие личности в современных условиях.

Ключевые слова: культура, коммуникация, профессиональная культура, этика, профессиональная коммуникация, профессиональная компетенция, иностранные языки

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Introduction

In contemporary society, there is a pressing demand for the incorporation of humanity into all facets of human existence and endeavors. This evolution places particular emphasis on the importance of spiritual values. Consequently, the issue of cultivating individuals who encompass not only professional expertise but also a cultured persona, equipped to serve as a progenitor of culture by generating and passing on cultural values to future generations, has surfaced. Hence, the challenges related to attaining a heightened level of cultural refinement take on distinct importance in the fabric of present-day societal dynamics.

The axiological foundation underpinning the relationship between language and professional culture facilitates an examination of the role of values in shaping the professional culture of an expert. Within this framework, culture represents the diverse mechanisms through which individuals affirm their presence in the world, with language emerging as a pivotal avenue for self-assertion within the realm of their professional engagements. Given the paramount significance of linguistic context, a thorough exploration of the intricate interplay between linguistic and cultural processes becomes imperative when navigating the terrain of professional culture [5].

The pronounced specialized orientation characterizing contemporary higher education has engendered a dilution of shared cultural underpinnings that ought to underlie professional pedagogy, engendering discordance between professional practice and cultural ideals. Moreover, the training imparted to graduates of non-linguistics disciplines fails to align comprehensively with prevailing cultural and axiological paradigms.

The circumstance is notably pertinent for forthcoming professionals in technical domains. Their proficiency in language falls short of contemporary demands, and the cultivation of cultural values among future specialists is hindered by a crisis in universal values, a lack of developed value awareness, and the rejection of overarching cultural tenets.

The *main objective* of this study is to explore the connection between foreign language acquisition and the cultivation of overall cultural enrichment, with a

specific emphasis on both general cultural development and professional culture, among non-humanities university students. The research aims to investigate how the process of learning a foreign language influences the shaping of students' general cultural awareness as well as their proficiency in navigating professional cultural contexts within non-humanitarian academic settings.

Theoretical framework

Although the link between language and the professional culture of technical experts has garnered attention in domestic scholarly investigations, this subject has yet to undergo in-depth and comprehensive exploration in cultural studies.

Existing research on this matter tends to approach the issue of professional culture through the lenses of psychology, deontology, philology, ethics, and similar disciplines. However, cultural studies seem to have only superficially explored this dilemma, indicating the need for more thorough investigation to fully understand its implications. In the realm of academia, there exists a gap that requires critical analysis and research to shed light on the complexities surrounding the intersection of language proficiency, cultural competency, and the contemporary standards within technical fields.

The contemporary specialist is not merely defined by their proficiency in a particular field but by their ability to navigate the intricate interplay between their professional domain and the broader expanse of universal culture. This new breed of professionals is expected to possess a unique set of competencies that transcend traditional knowledge and technical skills, encompassing a rich tapestry of spiritual, ethical, and social dimensions.

As society propels forward into an era of constant innovation and cultural flux, the role of the modern specialist becomes increasingly multifaceted. Professionals must not only adapt to the ever-changing landscapes of their respective fields but also possess the foresight to embrace diverse professional, socio-cultural, and scientific challenges [3]. This entails not only staying abreast of the latest developments but also cultivating a deep understanding of the cultural and ideological underpinnings that shape their work.

In light of these evolving demands, the concept of professional culture has undergone a metamorphosis, placing heightened emphasis on qualities such as competence, broad professional acumen, and a profound sense of cultural literacy. Thus, in this paper we focus on the definition of a modern specialist as a *person who is called upon to embody a harmonious blend of technical prowess, intellectual acumen, social maturity, and innovative thinking, forging a path towards a new paradigm of excellence in the contemporary professional landscape* [4].

Culture plays a pivotal role in shaping both collective societal norms and individual identities, exuding a profound influence across diverse realms of social interaction and personal growth. This significant influence of culture extends beyond mere superficial manifestations, permeating deep into the intricate fabric of human existence and exerting a potent force in the intricate processes of personality development.

Furthermore, culture serves as a dynamic reservoir of shared beliefs, values, customs, and traditions that not only reflect the collective identity of a society but also contribute to the formation of individual personality traits and behaviors. The rich tapestry of cultural experiences and practices provides individuals with a multifaceted framework within which they navigate their social interactions, construct their self-identities, and interpret the world around them.

The reciprocal relationship between culture and personality development underscores the intricate interplay between societal norms, individual experiences, and psychological growth. As individuals internalize cultural values and norms, they engage in a complex process of identity negotiation, wherein they selectively incorporate and reinterpret cultural elements to forge a unique sense of self within the broader societal context.

In essence, *culture emerges as a foundational pillar upon which the edifice of personality is constructed, shaping the cognitive, emotional, and behavioral dimensions of individuals in profound ways*. The interconnection between cultural influences and personality development underscores the intricate web of dynamic interactions that define human experience, shedding light on the intricate pathways through which culture molds and transforms individual identities within the broader tapestry of societal structures [7].

Another words, culture is the process, result and qualitative level of activity, so the connection of any professional activity with culture is essential. If we conceptualize professional engagement as a fundamental aspect of human existence, then culture emerges as a conduit through which human life and activity find expression, delineating professional activity as a distinctive manifestation within the broader spectrum of human existence. The cultivation of a professional culture within an individual's personality represents a focal point of interest across various academic disciplines, including social psychology, philosophy, applied cultural studies, social anthropology, linguistics, and sociology. Despite its significance, the exploration of professional culture remains relatively underdeveloped within the realm of cultural studies, primarily attributable to the inherent complexities associated with comprehending the fundamental nature of the concept of "professional culture."

The scarcity of a cohesive framework that comprehensively elucidates the key attributes of "professional culture", encompassing its essence, content, and structure, poses a substantial challenge, thereby impeding the formulation of deep theoretical insights and pragmatic methodologies for its cultivation. Consequently, a dearth of in-depth theoretical analyses and practical strategies hinders the comprehensive understanding and development of professional culture within individuals.

Nevertheless, the current socio-cultural landscape underscores the imperative for a rigorous and scholarly examination of this issue in response to the evolving demands of societal evolution.

Contemporary scholarship views professional culture as a composite framework comprising a constellation of socially significant personal attributes that underpin the efficacy and prosperity of professional endeavors. This multifaceted amalgamation of qualities serves as a cornerstone for facilitating the attainment of professional excellence and proficiency within diverse occupational spheres, reflecting the intricate interplay between personal traits, societal expectations, and professional accomplishments [1].

Hence, in this paper, the term *"professional culture" is to be considered as the intricate amalgamation of attitudes, behaviors, values, and norms that characterize the interactions and practices within a specific professional domain*.

Nonetheless, a consensus among scholars regarding the extent of the interplay between enhancing an individual's general cultural knowledge, fostering professional culture, and influencing the outcomes of one's professional endeavors is notably lacking.

Thus, within the framework of the paper, it is necessary to draw attention to the actuality of studying the concept of professional culture from the point of view of cultural studies and foreign language teaching studies.

Hypotheses and research questions

In this study, the hypothesis is proposed that a connection exists between the study of a foreign language in a non-language university and the development of professional culture among future specialists. The research aims to investigate the relationship between the development of linguistic and communicative competence and the growth of professional culture in individuals preparing for specific careers.

To support this investigation, the following questions are posed: What is the nature of the link between the enhancement of linguistic and communicative skills and the fostering of professional culture in future specialists? How significantly do communication skills affect the growth of professional culture, and what tools are currently available for enhancing these skills in non-language-focused universities within the contemporary educational system?

Furthermore, the study seeks to explore potential strategies and modifications within the current educational framework of teaching foreign languages in non-language universities that could contribute to fortifying the cultivation of professional culture as an integral component of professional competence.

Discussion

Engaging in a profession involves an individual's dynamic and purposeful interaction within the societal context, directed towards the attainment of predetermined objectives. It entails a series of impactful social deeds executed by the individual through diverse methods to accomplish specific outcomes [5]. Occupation serves as the gateway for an individual to integrate into the intricate network of societal labor divisions and interactions, where one hones their professional skills and nurtures their unique professional ethos.

The essence of human life is grounded on the principle of serving others, a principle particularly essential in professions involving direct human interactions. These roles showcase a practitioner's drive to excel in their craft, aiming for optimal professional connections with a focus on the human element.

A pivotal factor in the development of a professional is the ability to discover personal significance within their work. When an individual perceives their profession as more than just a job but as a core aspect of their identity, they engage with the world around them in a profound manner, fostering both personal growth and professional expertise. Viewing professional engagement as a life purpose harmonizes the demands of the profession with the practitioner's innate qualities, thus enhancing their professional acumen.

Professional aptitude, therefore, can be viewed as the capacity to excel not just in one's field but also as an individual. A seasoned professional embodies confidence, self-assurance, knowledge, proactive decision-making skills, and a strong sense of independence.

Authentic professionals take pride in their work, willingly accept responsibility for their actions, and put in the effort to do their best. Consequently, the growth of professional skills and personal development go hand in hand and need to be considered together.

Contemporary research extensively delves into the intricacies surrounding the cultivation of expertise across various fields, which serves as a pivotal element in shaping the professional ethos of an individual.

Professionalism is depicted as a holistic attribute of an individual, encompassing proficiency in the field, ethical conduct, pro-activeness, and proficiency as enduring features, alongside the capacity for self-improvement [12]. Advanced specialized education aims at nurturing professional skills, denoting a professional's adeptness in applying theoretical knowledge, practical skills, and competencies. A professional's competence is influenced by their experiences, personal traits, thirst for self-improvement, creative disposition, and conscientious approach to their endeavors.

The development of professional skills is a unique journey for each individual. The process of

honing professional competence is influenced by the nature of the work and the social context, constituting the amalgamation of a professional's traits. This amalgamation involves adeptly mastering knowledge, skills, and abilities while embodying socially valued personal attributes.

Continuous aspirations to enhance one's professional standing are essential indicators of a specialist's competence. This improvement should stem from a solid foundation of high professional ethics and proficiency. Furthermore, the development of professional ethics necessitates a broad spectrum of cultural and social skills in a specialist, serving as the fundamental building block for its evolution. Consequently, as experts cultivate their professional ethics, they must intentionally align their work with the overarching socio-cultural values, recognizing the inseparable connection between the "social" and "cultural" aspects [7].

Professional culture represents a unique realm within a professional group, embodying benchmarks of expertise and capability that define the community's standards. This notion encompasses not only the established practices and customs within a specific professional circle but also the societal relationships prevalent at a particular stage of its progression. The composition of professional culture is intricate, encompassing a framework of overarching cultural values intrinsic to professional undertakings, along with a repertoire of spiritual dimensions and distinct components.

The attainment and refinement of professional culture epitomize a catalyst for the enhancement of professional aptitude, relying on a foundation of theoretical knowledge, practical proficiency, abilities, and accumulated experience essential for a specific field. Serving as a crucial gauge of an individual's social maturity, professional culture embodies a prerequisite for engaging in socially significant pursuits, while also reflecting an individual's broader cultural acumen exhibited throughout their professional endeavors [2].

Professionally significant attributes encompass ethical norms, the ethical stance of a practitioner, a comprehensive comprehension and analysis of cultural phenomena locally and globally. Nevertheless, amidst these critical dimensions, the contemporary realm often overlooks the pivotal role of language etiquette, communicative skills, and verbal eloquence.

This trifecta not only serves as a crucial component but also acts as a distinctive hallmark of professional competence, warranting a comprehensive examination and acknowledgment within the scholarly discourse [3].

Numerous scholars posit that the emergence of culture as a phenomenon is contingent upon human engagement in communication processes. Upon entering the professional domain, individuals become integral parts of interpersonal networks, thereby significantly shaping the trajectory of their subsequent professional endeavors based on their capacity to navigate various situations with appropriateness. This highlights the intricate interplay between communication, cultural dynamics, and professional efficacy, underscoring the paramount importance of adept interpersonal skills in professional settings [1].

Communication culture, cultivated during one's professional engagement, is intricately intertwined with and should be examined in conjunction with such endeavors. Consequently, communication within the professional sphere is considered a distinct form of engagement that serves as a means to accomplish primary vocational tasks and aligns with the overarching objectives of the profession.

Given that a specialist's proficiency in communication significantly influences the success of their professional pursuits, it warrants classification as a trait of paramount importance. A person's communicative adeptness is exemplified through their interpersonal interactions, adept management of behavior, effective argumentation, manipulation of the interlocutor's persona, strategic attainment of communication objectives through verbal and non-verbal strategies, and adept navigation of potential conflict scenarios. This underpins the pivotal role of communication prowess in fostering professional excellence and underscores its contribution to achieving desired outcomes in professional settings.

The communication culture within the contemporary specialist's professional realm encompasses not only the guidelines of official ethics in communication but also professional speech decorum, proficiency in behavioral and speech etiquette norms. Disregarding the nuances of communicative exchanges with colleagues can result in confrontations that might be circumvented through adherence to a universal ethical

code, applicable to all individuals irrespective of their professional status or social roles.

During communicative engagements, individuals wield speech as a tool to exert influence on other participants, with the primary aim being persuasion. Individuals articulate with the intent to sway, whether it be shaping behaviors, thoughts, emotions, or consciousness of others. The efficacy of communicative exchanges hinges on the extent of mastery over speech.

In the contemporary landscape, nearly all professional undertakings necessitate communication and interpersonal dialogues. Consequently, ethics holds a paramount position among the core factors that mold and orchestrate collective human endeavors, hence the foundational role of communicative ethics in specialist training.

As an integral part of a specialist's professional demeanor, communicative ethics plays a pivotal role in averting psychological hurdles and enhancing the efficacy of interpersonal and professional collaborations. It upholds principles such as rational reasoning, pursuit of consensus through dialogue, and aligns with professional ethics without conflicting with universal moral standards [6].

The moral dimension of communication entails adhering to universally recognized codes of conduct, exhibiting reverence towards communication partners, demonstrating kindness, empathy, emotional self-regulation, and an ability to empathize with the emotions of others. Cultural awareness aims to foster open-mindedness and tolerance in human interactions, acknowledging that what is acceptable in one context may not be suitable in another. E.g. Cicero emphasized the importance of understanding the appropriateness of speech, highlighting its significance in both verbal discourse and daily interactions.

Ethical standards in communication form an essential component of an individual's professional ethos. Each professional cultivates a unique communication style influenced by their personal values and the ethical beliefs specific to their professional community. Communicative ethics, to some extent, mirrors the moral fabric of society and its foundational ethical principles.

Expanding on the concept of cultural sensitivity, it serves as a bridge towards fostering mutual understanding, fostering inclusivity, and nurturing harmonious relationships across diverse contexts and backgrounds. By embracing ethical communication practices, individuals can navigate a spectrum of social dynamics with grace, enhancing the quality of interactions and promoting a culture of respect and empathy in both personal and professional spheres [14].

The concept of professional communication culture is exemplified as a compilation of ethical guidelines and standards that govern human interaction within the professional realm. Every professional culture is constructed upon the societal norms and regulations prevalent in contemporary society. Certain behaviors and strategies for achievement are recognized as permissible and widely embraced, setting a benchmark for emulation, while others are discarded. The unique culture of each society plays a role in shaping individuals, imparting upon them the characteristics of socially accepted behavioral standards.

Acquiring a refined level of culture within professional communication necessitates not only the acquisition of knowledge pertaining to relevant subjects, processes, and relationships but also the internalization of norms that hold significance within the professional domain. Delving deeper into the complexities of professional communication demands a comprehensive understanding of the ethical principles that underpin interpersonal interactions in a professional setting, facilitating effective collaboration and fostering harmonious relationships within the workplace [15].

Establishing harmonious interactions among individuals within a professional team is facilitated by a set of standards intended to foster cooperative and deliberate collaboration. These standards aim to improve the reliability, consistency, uniformity, and clarity of communication participants' conduct.

The behavioral ethos of professionals striving for success primarily hinges on adhering to the recognized norms and guidelines prevalent within contemporary professional circles. These norms are influenced by the conventions, practices, ceremonies, and regulations of a specific culture, and are inherently linked to cultural values, which serve as the fundamental pillars of all cultural expressions.

In cultivating a conducive environment for professional growth and achievement, it is imperative to embrace and embody the principles that govern effective communication, collaboration, and conduct within the professional sphere. By upholding these norms and values, individuals can navigate the complexities of professional interactions with authenticity, integrity, and respect, thereby fostering a culture of mutual trust, cooperation, and success [2]. The beliefs that individuals uphold shape their perspectives and serve as driving forces for behaviors displayed within specific cultural groups. These values, deeply ingrained in the fabric of society, not only define the way people perceive the world but also play a crucial role in motivating individuals to engage in activities that align with their cultural identity.

Given this, the establishment of professional standards must be viewed in relation to core beliefs, as values play a pivotal role in guiding human actions within a cultural setting. Professionals draw on these values as guiding principles that underpin their decisions and actions in the workplace, influencing the way they interact with colleagues, clients, and the broader community.

Values serve as the cornerstone of any society, offering insights into the essence of existence, individuality, and the significance of experiences and deeds in one's life. Professionals rely on values to differentiate between truths and falsehoods, fairness and injustice, what is acceptable and what is not, among other distinctions. These values not only shape their ethical compass but also inform their sense of purpose and direction in their chosen field.

Norms, values, and meanings are integrated into human behaviors and activities, shaping customary conduct. Through the incorporation of these values into everyday practices, individuals internalize cultural norms, reinforcing behaviors that are deemed appropriate within their social context. This continuous reinforcement not only helps maintain societal order but also fosters a sense of unity and belonging among community members.

Apart from universally acknowledged human values, the professional environment showcases distinct values prevalent within the community. These specific values, unique to each professional group, reflect the shared principles and beliefs that guide their

interactions and decision-making processes. By upholding these professional values, practitioners demonstrate their commitment to their craft and contribute to the collective identity of their professional community.

The influence and importance of values in individual lives are shaped by the culture they belong to, with its distinctive features and characteristics playing a defining role in this regard. As individuals navigate the complexities of cultural norms and values, they contribute to the rich tapestry of human diversity, highlighting the interconnectedness of values, culture, and personal identity in shaping human experiences and interactions [6].

The foundational element of communication culture holds immense significance in enhancing the efficacy of professional interactions. Achieving success in professional communication demands a deep understanding of the social and linguistic norms and the capability to apply them with precision during discourse. Delving into the essence of a "communication culture" unveils a diverse spectrum of intangible and tangible manifestations of human cohabitation and engagement within a societal domain characterized by multifaceted, balanced, and comparable cultural elements. Additionally, it necessitates a particular mindset among individuals towards embracing and celebrating this amalgamation of diverse cultures within a shared social environment.

Effective professional communication hinges on the integration of normative standards and cultural nuances, underscoring the importance of cultural literacy and linguistic competence. The concept of a "communication ethos" embodies the complexity of interpersonal dialogues, encompassing a kaleidoscope of cultural expressions and social interplays within a dynamic and heterogeneous societal context. At its essence, this ethos calls for a mindful appreciation of the diverse cultural fabric that shapes professional landscapes, emphasizing the value of mutual respect and understanding in fostering meaningful communication exchanges.

In the context of professional engagements, adept knowledge of communication conventions and cultural sensibilities plays a pivotal role in facilitating productive dialogues. This entails not only a proficiency in navigating social mores and linguistic norms

but also a keen awareness of the intricate dynamics of cultural exchange. Within the framework of a vibrant "communication ethos," individuals are encouraged to embrace the richness of cultural diversity and the multiplicity of viewpoints that characterize their social milieu.

The heart of effective professional communication lies in the seamless integration of linguistic adeptness and cultural insight, guiding individuals towards successful interactions in diverse settings. The ethos of a "communication culture" embodies the intricate dance of human interactions, weaving together a tapestry of cultural nuances and social dynamics within a tapestry of diverse traditions and beliefs. Embracing this ethos requires a conscious commitment to fostering inclusivity and empathy, paving the way for authentic and meaningful connections in the professional sphere [4].

Given that fostering a persona adept at absorbing and shaping culture through dialogue stands as a key prerequisite for today's professionals, possessing refined communication abilities emerges as a crucial trait for individuals in the workforce.

The contemporary professional realm craves individuals who exhibit a commitment to continual self-improvement, where information literacy emerges as a pivotal facet shaping the professional ethos.

The inclination and aptitude for perpetual learning and knowledge acquisition serve as catalysts in advancing one's professional acumen and consequently, the overall cultural refinement of prospective experts. As a result, there exists a symbiotic relationship between culture and education: culture acts as a prerequisite for education, while education serves as a catalyst for cultural advancement.

Contemplating the evolving landscape of the modern workforce, it becomes evident that honing the capacity to absorb and mold culture via interactive discourse is indispensable for effective professionals. The contemporary professional arena increasingly demands individuals who exhibit a steadfast dedication to continuous self-improvement, wherein possessing a high level of information literacy becomes paramount in shaping one's professional competencies. The innate drive and ability to engage in perpetual learning and knowledge acquisition play a pivotal role in not

only fostering one's professional growth but also cultivating a nuanced cultural perspective among emerging specialists. This intricate interplay between culture and education underscores the interdependent nature of these realms: culture serving as a prerequisite for educational pursuits, while education serves as a conduit for cultural enrichment and progression.

Nonetheless, a notable deficiency persists in the cultivation of fundamental aspects of personality development in aspiring professionals, such as ethics, ethical communication, a broad understanding of culture, and the enhancement of communication etiquette. In the current educational landscape, the emphasis on technical disciplines predominates in the training of students pursuing technical specializations. The intricate web of demanding curricula and the rigorous nature of technical training inevitably relegates the role of general humanities in shaping the holistic development of future specialists. *Consequently, while students acquire essential competencies crucial for success in their professional endeavors, they are compelled to forego the acquisition of other competencies that, as previously established, hold substantial sway over their professional trajectory.*

The prevailing educational paradigm falls short in nurturing the essential elements that form the bedrock of a well-rounded professional persona. Ethics, ethical communication, a comprehensive grasp of cultural nuances, and the refinement of interpersonal communication skills represent vital facets that warrant deliberate attention and integration within the educational framework. Presently, the educational landscape predominantly tilts towards the primacy of technical disciplines in the grooming of students pursuing technical specializations. The exhaustive curricular demands and the intricate nature of technical training inadvertently overshadow the pivotal role that general humanities play in fostering a comprehensive developmental trajectory for future specialists. Consequently, while students adeptly acquire requisite competencies essential for navigating the complexities of their professional pursuits, they are compelled to forego the cultivation of other vital competencies that, as elucidated earlier, exert a profound influence on their professional journey.

The lacuna in prioritizing the development of ethical principles, ethical communication channels, cultural awareness, and communication decorum in aspiring specialists highlights a systemic flaw in the present educational paradigm. The predominant focus on technical subjects in the training of students pursuing technical fields results in a constrained allocation of resources and attention towards nurturing the holistic development aspects essential for future professionals. The rigorous academic demands and the extensive scope of technical training inadvertently sideline the formative role that humanities disciplines play in fostering a well-rounded professional persona. While students effectively acquire technical proficiencies requisite for excelling in their chosen fields, the trade-off comes at the expense of neglecting other crucial competencies that, as established earlier, profoundly influence their professional journey and outlook.

Currently, the cultivation of communicative abilities among students in non-linguistic and technical disciplines occurs predominantly through foreign language programs within higher education institutions. The need of foreign language acquirement in terms of specialists training is increasing dramatically. As it was mentioned by Rybak M.V., 'in the course of nonlinguistic university the foreign language is considered not as a comprehensible independent subject, but as a source of new information in the field of specialization' [9].

Conclusion and future directions

Thus, the necessity and significance of incorporating foreign language studies into academic curricula persist as an essential component of educational frameworks. Within the confines of traditional classroom settings dedicated to foreign language instruction, students not only gain proficiency in specialized vocabulary and fundamental communication skills in a foreign language, but they also delve into the exploration of the professional culture associated with the target language's country. Through this process, students learn to articulate their ideas effectively and select appropriate linguistic structures within diverse contextual frameworks, particularly within professional contexts.

It is commonly observed that the articulation of thoughts in a foreign language often requires conceptualizing ideas in the native language before transpos-

ing them into verbal expressions in the target language. This bridging process serves to enhance the overall communicative competencies of aspiring professionals. Furthermore, foreign language classes offer students a profound immersion into the cultural milieu of the target language's country. For students enrolled in non-linguistic disciplines, the primary objective of foreign language acquisition extends beyond linguistic proficiency to encompass an immersive understanding of professional landscapes and cultural dynamics relevant to the studied language's country. This holistic approach not only enriches students' intercultural competence but also nurtures a nuanced appreciation of global professional practices and cultural diversity.

Within the realm of foreign language instruction, students are afforded the opportunity to engage in comparative analyses aimed at elucidating insights and making informed assessments regarding the professional culture of Russia. Through such comparative endeavors, students can discern the merits and demerits of the Russian professional culture when juxtaposed with the cultural norms of the target language's country. This analytical approach enables students to acquire a nuanced understanding of cross-cultural dynamics and fosters critical thinking skills within the domain of professional culture assessment.

However, a prevailing challenge persists in many non-language academic institutions, wherein foreign language courses are constrained by time limitations, thereby impeding the thorough development of communicative competencies and the cultivation of business acumen, professional decorum, and ethical communication practices. The constrained temporal scope of these language courses poses a significant obstacle to the comprehensive nurturing of students' linguistic proficiency and intercultural awareness within the realms of professional discourse and ethical communication protocols. Consequently, the abbreviated nature of such language programs diminishes the potential for students to attain a well-rounded skill set essential for effective cross-cultural interactions and proficiency in navigating diverse professional contexts.

The evolution of foreign language education within the academic landscape has undergone signifi-

cant transformations over the years. In the past, foreign languages and humanitarian studies received ample academic time and emphasis, facilitating in-depth exploration of linguistic and cultural dimensions. However, contemporary pedagogical practices in higher education institutions often allocate limited time to foreign language instruction, particularly in non-language oriented disciplines. This temporal constraint hinders the comprehensive development of students' communicative skills, intercultural competencies, and understanding of professional cultures.

Given the increasing reliance on technological solutions to streamline processes and optimize time utilization in modern society, there arises a critical need to reassess the prioritization of foreign language learning within the curricula of technical specialties and non-language universities. The historical precedents of allocating substantial academic time to foreign language education underscore the inherent value of linguistic proficiency and cross-cultural awareness in fostering well-rounded and globally competent professionals. Furthermore, the emphasis on

communication and cultural aspects of foreign language education should be heightened within the existing curricula of non-language-focused universities. Further studies are needed to determine the specific adjustments that should be made to programs from linguistic and cultural perspectives.

Therefore, it is the best moment to underscore the imperative of enhancing the prominence of foreign language instruction for students pursuing technical disciplines and those enrolled in non-language programs. By incorporating holistic language acquisition programs into the contemporary higher education structure, future specialists can acquire vital communication proficiencies, intercultural awareness, and a sophisticated comprehension of professional norms, thus arming themselves with the necessary competencies to excel in varied and interlinked global settings. This integration underscores the pivotal role of English language studies in not only enhancing core competencies but also in fostering a heightened cultural acumen that can have a transformative impact on broader societal dynamics.

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